

TOWARDS INCLUSIVE EDUCATION: A STUDY ON TEACHERS' ATTITUDES TOWARD HOMOSEXUALITY

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 20

Issue 6

Pages: 658-673

Document ID: 2024PEMJ1886

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11501052

Manuscript Accepted: 05-07-2024

Towards Inclusive Education: A Study on Teachers' Attitudes toward Homosexuality

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Abstract

This study investigates educators' attitudes toward homosexuality and its implications for fostering inclusivity within educational environments. Key objectives include profiling respondents based on age, sexual orientation, religion, and educational attainment, exploring predominant attitudes of teachers toward homosexuality, assessing differences in attitudes across demographic groups, and examining correlations between attitudes and demographic profiles. A descriptive-correlational design was employed with a survey administered online to 89 secondary school teachers as data collection technique. The statistical analysis involved frequency and percent distributions, weighted means, standard deviation, One-Way ANOVA, and Pearson Product Moment Correlation. The results revealed that the largest age group was 31-40 years old (32.6%), with 50.6% identifying as heterosexual females, 25.8% are homosexuals, and 23.6% as heterosexual males. Majority were Roman Catholic (75.3%) and held a bachelor's degree (67.4%). Generally, attitudes towards homosexuality were positive, with mean scores ranging from 3.62 to 4.10, but there were also instances of disagreement or neutrality (mean scores of 2.43 to 2.81), indicating a mix of acceptance and hesitation. Negative attitudes were generally less common, reflecting wider trends of increased acceptance and tolerance (mean scores of 1.85 to 3.48). Homosexuals had distinct attitudes compared to heterosexual males ($p=.000$, $.008$) in both positive and negative aspects, while heterosexual females differed from homosexuals only in positive attitudes ($p=.008$). Among the demographic profiles, only the teachers' sexual orientation showed significant relationship with their positive attitudes ($F=9.837$, $p=.000$) and negative attitudes ($F=4.945$, $p=.009$) toward homosexuality. The study emphasizes the importance of understanding attitudes towards homosexuality in educational environments and offers insights for promoting inclusivity.

Keywords: *attitudes, homosexuality, sexual orientation, correlation, secondary school teachers*

Introduction

In recent years, the Philippines has strengthened its dedication to incorporating gender equality into its education system through laws. For the School Year 2022-2023, the Department of Education has emphasized the rigorous enforcement of DepEd Order No. 32, s. 2017, also known as the "Gender Responsive Basic Education Policy," across all elementary and high schools throughout the country. This policy provides guidelines for DepEd employees to support and protect the rights of all children, regardless of sexual orientation, and create a caring learning environment for all (Department of Education, 2017). This is also concordant with Article 14, Section 14 of the 1987 Constitution, which advocates for gender equality, and the 2009 Philippine Magna Carta for Women, which establishes a framework that promotes non-discrimination and gender equality in policy development and implementation (Republic Act No. 9710). Within the realm of education, it reiterates the right to equal access and the eradication of discrimination in educational opportunities, scholarships, and training programs (Republic Act No. 9710). This legal foundation underscores the Philippines' commitment to ensuring gender equality in various sectors, including education.

Moreover, discussions by Cimene et al. (2023,2023) delve into the multifaceted challenges and opportunities associated with implementing inclusive education within the Philippine educational landscape. These challenges encompass policy frameworks that need to be inclusive, comprehensive teacher training programs to support diverse learning needs, adequate infrastructure to facilitate inclusive learning environments, and active community participation to foster a culture of inclusion and acceptance among students with diverse backgrounds. This discourse underscores the complex interplay of legal mandates, policy frameworks, and practical challenges in achieving inclusive education in the Philippines. It highlights the importance of a holistic approach that integrates legal provisions, policy initiatives, and practical strategies to create an educational system that caters to the needs of all learners, regardless of their individual differences.

Also, DepEd introduced Order No. 40, s. 2012, outlining policies to safeguard children in schools from various forms of abuse, including discrimination, violence, and bullying. This order highlights sexual orientation as a recognized basis for discrimination (Department of Education, 2012). The enactment of Republic Act (RA) No. 10533 in 2013 marked the initiation of the K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum program. The Implementing Rules and Regulations (Rule II, Section 10.2) of this act mandates the Department of Education to ensure that the basic education curriculum is sensitive to gender and culture. Additionally, in 2013, Republic Act No. 10627, otherwise known as the Anti-Bullying Law of 2013, was passed by Congress, explicitly forbidding bullying and harassment based on sexual orientation and gender identity.

Cimene et al. (2020) pointed out that while these steps are valuable to having more accepting and gender-inclusive schools, the country has yet to understand the wide spectrum of human sexuality fully. Relative to this, Competente (2021) stressed that despite the

Philippines being a strong advocate of integrating gender equality into the principles, goals, and processes of Philippine education and having decriminalized homosexuality, the full realization of LGBT acceptance in the country is still a work in progress. Tang and Poudel (2018) discovered that the living conditions of Filipino LGBT students are slowly changing. This is marked by insufficient legal safeguards, mental health difficulties, and opposition from religious perspectives.

The introduction of these policies strongly conveys that bullying and discrimination are unacceptable and should have no place in educational institutions. However, despite their strong nature on paper, these policies have not been effectively enforced in schools. Notably, DepEd has not outlined specific mechanisms for implementing DepEd Order No. 32 in educational institutions (De La Fuente, undated). Competente (2021) emphasized that while the policy shows promise, the implementation of effective practices for handling students' and teachers' sexual orientation and addressing homophobia still needs to be established. Through findings in group discussions, Reloj (2021) found out that some students encountered obstacles, such as facing homophobic slurs in the classroom. Instructors making negative examples about LGBTQ+ individuals caused discomfort, leading some to skip school and seek support in gay groups during their coming-out process due to a lack of support programs for those facing familial opposition to their sexual orientations.

To address this gap, this concept paper lies in the imperative to address and understand the attitudes and behaviors of teachers towards homosexuality within the Philippine educational context. With evolving societal attitudes, it is crucial to explore how these key stakeholders perceive and engage with issues related to sexual orientation. This study seeks to contribute valuable insights to the ongoing discourse on creating inclusive, respectful, and safe learning environments for all students, regardless of their sexual orientation.

Objective of the Study. This study underscored the potential impact on fostering inclusivity within educational settings. This study aims to reveal predominant attitudes among educators toward homosexuality. This study is crucial for creating a more accepting and inclusive educational environment, in line with worldwide efforts for diversity and inclusion.

Research Questions

The study addresses the following key problem statements:

1. What is the demographic profile of the respondents in terms of the following:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sexual orientation;
 - 1.3. religion; and
 - 1.4. educational attainment?
2. What are the positive and negative attitudes of teachers toward homosexuality in schools?
3. Is there a significant difference between the respondents' attitudes toward homosexuality when grouped according to their demographic profile?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' attitudes toward homosexuality and their demographic profile?

Literature Review

In a diverse society, educators and policymakers need to create inclusive and welcoming educational environments for all students and teachers (Kersey & Voigt, 2021) since a growing number of sexual minority students disclose their sexual orientations at school (Gato et al., 2020). With this, schools must ensure that the learning environment supports the education of all youth, including those who identify as LGBTQ+ or Lesbians, Gays, Bisexual, Transgender, Queer plus are questioning their sexual identity (Wimberly, 2015).

However, discrimination based on sexual orientation persists in school settings, as highlighted by Reloj (2021) and Russell, et al. (2021). In the Philippines, gay students often face physical, verbal, sexual, and cyber harassment in schools (Evans et al., 2017; Ferrer et al., (2020). Santos and De Jesus (2020) even state that LGBT student harassment have increasingly gained national attention as a serious issue that needs to be resolved. Additionally, many students are unaware of the available anti-bullying policies, and there is a lack of guidance for these individuals on how to cope with such situations and where to seek help (Human Rights Watch, 2017).

On campus, gay students frequently endure discrimination, isolation, and avoidance, as noted by Horn and Russell (2016). Their research emphasizes the prevalence of harassment related to social identity, such as sexual orientation, in many schools. Homophobic harassment stands out as the most common form, leading to increased negative treatment. Kiapoka's (2020) study also reveals alarming rates, with approximately one in seven children experiencing physical harassment or violence due to their sexual orientation (14.6%), gender (12.6%), and/or gender expression (19.3%). In hostile school environments, Santos and De Jesus (2020) and Steck and Perry (2018) found out that LGBT students primarily encounter verbal/written bullying, causing negative emotional impacts such as anxiety. While various forms of bullying occasionally occur, including physical, social/relational, and cyberbullying, Tang and Poudel's (2018) findings indicate a slow progression in the living environment of Filipino LGBT students, characterized by a lack of legal protection, mental health challenges, and religious opposition.

Recent research, including Cardinal (2021), also highlights the adverse impact of disparities and heteronormative school culture on

LGBTQ individuals. LGBTQ youth, as evidenced by studies like Colvin et al. (2020), Hatchel et al. (2019), and Steck and Perry (2018), face elevated risks of peer victimization, discrimination, and harassment compared to heterosexual counterparts. This vulnerability extends to academic struggles, notably high dropout rates (Snapp et al., 2015; Steck & Perry, 2018; Wimberly, 2015). Furthermore, LGBTQ individuals experiencing gender victimization are more likely to report substance abuse, depression, anxiety, and suicidality (Colvin et al., 2020; Hatchel et al., 2019; Chan et al., 2022; Seelman et al., 2017.) Also, Hanimoglu (2019) emphasizes the higher suicide risk among LGBT students, partly attributed to schools being major sources of stigmatization. Schools are yet another major source of stigmatization for the LGBT students as they spend most of their time with other schoolmates.

In terms of Teachers' and Administrators' perspectives towards homosexuality, Competente (2021) found out that these key stakeholders in school have issues with homosexuality acceptance and that their attitudes lean to negative attitudes. In his study, the results show that many teachers and administrators attributed their hesitation to a lack of confidence in their knowledge about the expansiveness and complexities that these identities have to offer. It serves as a problem as teachers play an active role in cultivating a learning environment that allows for queer pedagogy and anti-oppressive education, requiring a need for reflexivity about their practices, opinions, and values, which may hold heteronormative bias. Goldstein et al. (2007), as cited by Kiapoka (2020), emphasize that teachers appear hesitant to support LGBT students in implementing measures aimed at creating safer and more welcoming school environments for this group of children. Instances where teachers attempt anti-homophobic and anti-transphobic actions often result in conflicts, either between teachers themselves or between teachers and students. Additionally, as stated in the findings of Wright and Smith (2013) referenced by Santos and De Jesus (2020), LGBT students in schools where administrators fail to address the use of homophobic and transphobic language frequently observe the tolerated contempt.

On the contrary, Feldman (2023) emphasizes that despite facing challenges in oppressive campus climates, LGBTQ students often exhibit high levels of resilience. Duran (2021) discovered that factors such as family, student organizations, and campus connections positively contribute to resilience in LGBTQ students. Nicolazzo (2017) argues that viewing resilience as an action involves identifying where and with whom one can succeed, allowing effective navigation of the learning environment. Zhang et al. (2019) highlighted that the more positive the teachers' attitudes are toward lesbians and gays, the more positive the children's attitudes are toward lesbians and gays. Studies indicate that positive relationships between teachers and LGBTQ students are linked to various advantages, including increased school engagement, improved academic performance, and overall better social-emotional well-being (Colvin et al., 2019; Day, Fish, et al., 2019; Day, Ioverno, et al., 2019). The adults in LGBT students' lives, both parents and teachers, who are key figures in the lives of LGBT students, possess firsthand insights into the daily experiences of sexually diverse youth. Teachers may offer a distinctive viewpoint on the peer relationships of LGBT students within the school environment, a significant part of children and adolescents' lives. (Kolbert et al., 2015).

In terms of correlation between teacher attitudes and homosexuality, past research on pre-service and in-service teachers examined a series of correlates, including age, gender, sexual orientation, and religiosity.

As of age, Herek and McLemore (2013) state that sexual prejudice becomes dysfunctional when antigay attitudes lead to social rejection rather than support, particularly in contexts where social norms favor LGBTQIA+ orientations. Younger individuals and those in more highly educated environments, such as college campuses, tend to exhibit more supportive attitudes. Teacher attitudes align with this pattern, with younger pre- and in-service teachers displaying lower levels of sexual prejudice and greater comfort addressing LGBTQIA+ issues compared to their older, more senior counterparts (Baiooco et al., 2020; Grigoropoulos, 2022; Hall & Rodgers, 2019; Page, 2017). Gegenfurtner et al. (2023) hypothesize that age is negatively correlated with teacher attitudes, predicting more positive attitudes among younger pre-service teachers.

As per the correlates between gender and teachers' attitudes towards LGBT, available evidence is mixed. While it may seem likely that men devalue individuals with non-heteronormative orientations to uphold their masculinity and heterosexuality (Herek & McLemore, 2013), several studies indicate insignificant gender differences in attitudes (Grigoropoulos, 2022; Hall & Rodgers, 2019; Stucky et al., 2020). These findings align with broader research, demonstrating higher levels of sexual prejudice and homonegative attitudes among heterosexual men teachers compared to heterosexual women teachers, particularly directed toward gay men (Gegenfurtner et al., 2023).

Regarding sexual orientation, the existing research is somewhat limited. Only three studies have explored attitude variations between heterosexual and homosexual teachers to our knowledge. Foy and Hodge (2016) and Stucky et al. (2020) found higher levels of prejudice among heterosexual teachers compared to homosexual teachers, while Hall and Rodgers (2019) reported that sexual orientation did not significantly predict LGBTQ teacher attitudes. Studies generally affirm that LGBTQIA+ community members share similar experiences of stigma and prejudice (Casey et al., 2019; Gegenfurtner & Gebhardt, 2017). Additionally, heterosexual individuals, in contrast to LGBT people, tend to feel a stronger need to uphold traditional gender roles, linked to more negative attitudes toward lesbian, gay, and bisexual individuals (Herek & McLemore, 2013). Thus, Gegenfurtner et al. (2023) propose the hypothesis that service teachers with non-heteronormative orientations may hold more positive views towards students with similar orientations compared to their heterosexual counterparts.

Another important indicator of homosexuality is gender, plays an important role in shaping attitudes towards homosexuality. Research adds that men tend to hold more negative attitudes towards homosexuality compared to women, although the gap has been decreasing over time. For instance, a study by Herek (2002) titled "Heterosexuals' Attitudes Toward Bisexual Men and Women in the United

States" found that men reported more negative attitudes towards both gay men and lesbians compared to women. Factors such as traditional masculinity norms, including beliefs about toughness and emotional stoicism, may contribute to men's negative attitudes towards homosexuality. Attitudes towards homosexuality often vary across different age groups, with younger generations generally exhibiting more accepting attitudes compared to older generations. For instance, Pew Research Center surveys conducted in the United States have shown a consistent trend of increasing acceptance of homosexuality across all age groups over the past few decades, with younger cohorts being more supportive. This trend is attributed to factors such as greater exposure to diverse perspectives through media and education, as well as changing societal norms.

Similarly to attitude, religion can strongly influence attitudes towards homosexuality, with individuals from more conservative religious backgrounds often expressing more negative views. Research by scholars like Herek (2002) and Haldeman (1994) has explored the relationship between religion and attitudes towards homosexuality. Haldeman's work titled "The Practice and Ethics of Sexual Orientation Conversion Therapy" discusses how religious beliefs can contribute to the stigmatization of homosexuality and influence efforts to change sexual orientation. However, it's important to note that attitudes within religious communities can vary widely, with some religious groups becoming increasingly accepting of LGBTQ+ individuals and advocating for LGBTQ+ rights. In the study of Peter et al., (2018), their study examines the influence of religious affiliation on lesbian, gay, bisexual, trans, two spirit, queer, and questioning (LGBTQ)-inclusive practices. Using data from a national survey of educators from pre-kindergarten to grade 12, multivariate analyses of variance models were employed in order to test the effects of religious affiliation on several LGBTQ-inclusive outcome measures. Results show that religious affiliation does have a significant impact on the likelihood that educators will (or will not) practice LGBTQ-inclusive education, however, the pathways to such practices vary considerably across religious groupings. Recommendations are suggested in terms of intervention, inclusive teaching practices, visibility, and leadership.

Moreover, educational attainment is associated with more positive attitudes towards homosexuality. Higher levels of education are often correlated with greater exposure to diverse perspectives and critical thinking skills, which can lead to increased acceptance of LGBTQ+ individuals. A study by Lewis (2009) titled "Educational Attainment and Attitudes Toward Homosexuality: An Analysis of African Public Opinion Surveys" found that higher levels of education were associated with more positive attitudes towards homosexuality in African countries. However, the relationship between education and attitudes towards homosexuality can be influenced by other factors such as cultural context and socioeconomic status. La Roi and Mandemakers (2018) added that higher educated people tend to be more accepting of homosexuality than lower educated people. This has inspired claims that education leads to a higher acceptance of homosexuality. Alternatively, the association between education and acceptance of homosexuality could be confounded by (un)observed family background and stable individual characteristics.

In fostering a more inclusive learning environment, teachers can play a crucial role as agents of social change when they receive empowerment through training, administrative support, and ongoing dialogue on diversity, equity, and inclusion. School, being a significant environment, offers an opportunity to address issues like sexual prejudice, marginalization, and oppression (Kosciw, 2017). Hall and Rodgers (2019) affirm that teachers have an ethical responsibility to see that all students, regardless of sexual orientation, receive a quality education. Santos and De Jesus (2020) concluded in their study that reducing bullying among LGBT students can be achieved by involving the affected individuals along with their school community (parents, teachers, administrators, and staff). It is crucial to include LGBT students in crafting stringent anti-bullying policies, encouraging them to voice their experiences to school authorities. Additionally, student programs should promote respect, school safety, and open discussions within the LGBT student population.

Moreover, it is essential for school leaders to challenge heteronormative perspectives that may prevail in schools and districts (Hernandez & Fraynd, 2014). School environments mirror broader societal dynamics and can vary in the levels of support from administrators, teachers, and students. Offering training during pre-service and in-service teacher sessions has the potential to bring about systemic change within schools (Stargell et al., 2020; Hall & Rodgers, 2019; Kiapoka, 2020). Zook, (2020) also emphasize that educational leaders must acknowledge that schools can be unwelcoming for LGBTQ+ individuals. Recognizing this is just the beginning. Creating fair learning environments involves taking courageous action to eliminate barriers and negative beliefs about LGBTQ+ people in the school culture.

Competente (2021) suggests better education for teachers and administrators on non-binary gender preferences to create a safe environment. This involves self-education and exposure to LGBTQ experiences through various platforms. Acceptance is conditional, often constrained by stereotypes. Schools should establish safe spaces for LGBTQ individuals, fostering understanding and adaptation to societal norms. Further research is needed, particularly exploring intersectional issues in rural and suburban schools, considering diverse teacher voices to illuminate the struggles of historically marginalized groups. Johnson et al. (2013) stress that several surveys examining discrimination against LGBT students highlight a correlation between discriminatory public policies and elevated mental disorder rates within the LGBT community. Addressing this, it is crucial to change existing school policies and culture to safeguard the well-being of LGBT students. Kiapoka (2020) then recommended that the programs should be designed according to a human rights perspective and include collaborative work among teachers, among teachers and parents and other stakeholders and among students.

Ensuring safe and inclusive schools for LGBTQ students requires a comprehensive, positive change approach. The harmful impact of

unsupportive environments emphasizes the urgent need for school reforms. Implementing zero-tolerance policies, LGBTQ-inclusive curricula, and mandatory professional development fosters diversity acceptance and rejects discrimination. Inclusive curricula raise awareness and validate the LGBTQ community, while professional development equips educators to support LGBTQ students. Creating safe spaces within schools is crucial for the physical and socio-emotional well-being of LGBTQ students, serving as a resource for challenges. Schools bear the responsibility to educate, protect, and support all students, including those who identify as LGBTQ (Cardinal, 2021).

Implementing evidence-based policies and fostering a peaceful environment, including support activities, can be effective in promoting the mental health of all students, especially those in the LGBT community. Research demonstrates that schools allowing the formation of Gay-Straight Alliances (GSAs) contribute to lower suicide rates, decreased class absenteeism, and reduced violence threats for LGBT students compared to schools lacking such support groups (Russell et al., 2016).

Moreover, Russell et al., (2016) recommend that schools should proactively prohibit violence, harassment, and bullying regardless of students' sexual orientation. Establishing safe spaces within the school environment, such as designated classrooms or counselors' offices, enables students to seek support freely. It is essential to incorporate information relevant to LGBT students, such as pregnancy prevention and awareness of HIV and other Sexually Transmitted Infections, into educational materials and curricula. Hanimoglu (2019) then highlights that schools should facilitate access to experienced community-based health providers for psychological, social, and counseling services.

Furthermore, Russell et al. (2021) outline strategies to enhance the safety and well-being of LGBTQ and all students in schools. Firstly, policies explicitly recognizing protected groups, like LGBTQ students, foster supportive environments for all youth. Secondly, professional development equips educators and school staff with tools to support and safeguard all students. Thirdly, providing access to information and support related to sexual orientation and gender identity or expression (SOGIE), along with SOGIE-inclusive curricula, offers resources and inclusion, shaping the school climate. Lastly, the presence of student-led clubs such as Gay-Straight Alliances (GSAs) enhance students' school experiences and well-being, contributing to a positive school climate.

In conclusion, the synthesis of literature examining the perspectives of teachers, administrators, and school environments towards homosexuality underscores the critical role these stakeholders play in shaping the experiences of LGBTQ+ individuals in educational settings. The reviewed studies have revealed a spectrum of attitudes, ranging from acceptance and support to reluctance and negative biases. The impact of these perspectives extends beyond individual interactions, influencing the broader school climate and contributing to challenges such as discrimination, harassment, and stigmatization faced by LGBTQ+ students.

This body of research serves as a crucial foundation for the current study, emphasizing the need for interventions, training programs, and policy reforms that foster a more inclusive and affirming educational environment. By exploring deeper into the complex and changing aspects of teacher attitudes and administrative perspectives, the present research aims to contribute various insights to the existing literature, ultimately striving towards creating safer, more welcoming spaces for all students, regardless of their sexual orientation.

Methodology

This study made use of the descriptive-correlational design, with the online self-administered survey as the technique for data collection. Data were obtained from 89 secondary school teachers.

The researchers utilized a two-part survey questionnaire. The first part gathered information on the profile of the participants such as: age, sexual orientation, religion, and educational attainment. The second part utilized a survey questionnaire based on the study of Boxill et al. (2011) to measure the teachers' attitude towards homosexuality.

For attitude questions, each sub-scale consists of ten (10) questions using a 5-point Likert Scale (5 - strongly agree, 4 - Agree, 3 - Neither agree nor disagree, 2 - Disagree and 1 - strongly disagree). Following Pallant's (2007) standards, overall, the test has good internal consistency (Cronbach alpha = 0.86) and adequate test-retest reliability (0.51). Mean scores were obtained for each construct and analyzed using PSPP - a free software application for analysis of sampled data, intended as a free alternative for IBM SPSS Statistics.

The research employed convenience sampling to select the representative samples, given the proximity to the accessible population, facilitated by the online administration of the survey-questionnaire. Survey data underwent statistical analysis employing frequency and percent distributions, weighted means, standard deviation, One-Way ANOVA, and Pearson Product Moment Correlation.

This study recognizes its limitations. The interpretation of findings and their implications should be contextualized within these limitations, primarily stemming from the sample utilized. The participants were exclusively drawn from secondary school teachers, and thus, the experiences documented may not be fully representative of the broader teaching community in the Philippines.

Despite efforts to ensure institutional diversity by recruiting from various disciplines, it is imperative to recognize that the cultural context of schools and regional norms, where the teachers are presently stationed, could have influenced their attitudes and subsequently impacted the results obtained. Moreover, it's worth noting that this study adheres strictly to ethical research standards, particularly

concerning obtaining free prior informed consent from all participants involved.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the data gathered among 89 respondents. The discussions of the results of this study are arranged in the same order as they are presented in the statement of the problem.

Table 1. *Distribution of the Respondents' Profile*

Profile	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
19-25	4	4.5
26-30	26	29.2
31-40	29	32.6
41-50	26	29.2
51-60	3	3.4
61 and above	1	1.1
Sexual Orientation		
Heterosexual Male	21	23.6%
Heterosexual Female	45	50.6%
Homosexual	23	25.8%
Religion		
Roman Catholic	67	75.3
Islam	3	3.4
Born Again Christian	19	21.3
Educational Attainment		
Bachelor's Degree	60	67.4
Master's Degree	23	25.8
Doctoral Degree	6	6.7

Table 1 shows the age of the respondents. It shows that 29 out of 89 respondents belong to the age bracket 31-40 years old representing the highest percentage 32.6% of the respondents. The second highest ranking age brackets are those respondents whose ages are 26-30 and 41-50 years old with 26 out of 89 respondents or 29.2 % of the respondents' population. The third highest-ranking percentage was with the age bracket 19-25 having 4.5% of the respondents' population. The fourth highest ranking 2 out of 89 respondents belongs to the age bracket 51-60 with 3.4 % of the respondents' population and the last was 1 out of 89 respondents or 1.1% of the respondents' population with age bracket 61 and above.

The data presents the distribution of respondents based on their sexual orientation. Of the 89 respondents surveyed, 45 identified as heterosexual females, representing 50.6% of the sample. Meanwhile, 23 respondents identified as homosexuals, accounting for 25.8% of the sample. Additionally, 21 respondents identified as heterosexual males, comprising 23.6% of the total respondents.

The table also presents the religious affiliations of the respondents. Among the 89 respondents surveyed, the largest religious group is Roman Catholic, with 67 individuals or 75.3% of the total population identifying as such. Following Born Again Christians which constitute the second-largest group, with 19 out of 89 respondents, representing 21.3% of the total population. The third group is comprised of individuals practicing Islam, with 3 out of 89 respondents, making up 3.4% of the total population.

The table displays the educational attainment of the respondents. Among the 89 respondents surveyed, the majority, comprising 60 individuals or 67.4% of the total, hold a bachelor's degree, making it the most common level of education among the sample. Following bachelor's degree holders, individuals who completed their master's degree constitute the second-largest group, with 23 out of 89 respondents, representing 25.8% of the total population. Finally, individuals with Doctoral Degrees form the smallest group, comprising 6 out of 88 respondents or 6.7% of the total population.

Table 2. *Respondents' Positive Attitudes Toward Homosexuality*

Positive Attitudes	Weighted Mean (N=89)	SD	Description
1. I would feel comfortable working closely with a homosexual.	4.10	.88	Agree
2. I would feel at ease talking to a homosexual person at a party.	3.98	.90	Agree
3. I would feel comfortable knowing that I am attractive to members of my sex.	2.81	1.22	Neither
4. I would feel comfortable if I learn that the best friend of my sex is homosexual.	3.62	.99	Agree
5. I would enjoy attending social functions at which homosexuals are present.	3.94	.87	Agree
6. I would feel comfortable if I learn that my son's/daughter's teacher is a homosexual.	3.81	.90	Agree
7. If a member of my sex makes an advance attempt towards me, I would feel flattered.	2.61	1.10	Neither
8. I would feel comfortable if a member of my sex makes advance attempt towards me.	2.43	1.04	Disagree
9. I would feel comfortable if I find myself attracted to a member of my sex	2.54	1.17	Disagree
10. I would feel comfortable communicating closely with a homosexual.	3.94	.79	Agree
Overall	3.38	.72	Neither

Legend: WM= Weighted Mean, 4.21-5.00 = Strongly Agree, 3.41-4.20 = Agree, 2.61-3.40 = Neutral, 1.81-2.60 = Disagree, 1.00-1.80 = Strongly Disagree

Table 2 presents the predominant attitudes of the respondents when prompted positive statements from the survey. The data reveal that statements such as feeling comfortable working closely with a homosexual (mean = 4.10), feeling at ease talking to a homosexual person at a party (mean = 3.98), enjoying attending social functions with homosexual people present (mean = 3.94), and feeling comfortable communicating closely with homosexuals ($W=3.94$) all demonstrate a high level of agreement among respondents. These responses suggest a general comfort and acceptance of interacting with homosexuals in various social and professional settings, indicating positive attitudes towards inclusivity and diversity. This aligns with the conclusions drawn by Hall and Rodgers (2019), Goldstein-Schultz (2022), and Gururaj et al. (2023) indicating a shift toward more positive attitudes among teachers toward homosexuality reflecting tolerance, acceptance, support, admiration, appreciation, and nurturance.

Similarly, respondents expressed agreement with the statement about feeling comfortable if the best friend of the same sex is homosexual (mean = 3.62) and if their child's teacher is homosexual (mean = 3.81), further indicating acceptance of homosexuals in personal relationships and educational environments. These are confirmed by the findings of the Dabra and Prasad (2021) stating that teachers have no inhibitions in talking to the people of the LGBT community or being friends with them. Similarly, Ploderl and Trembley (2015) conclude that the teachers have positive views of sexual minority individuals and found homosexuality an acceptable way of life.

However, the findings also reveal areas of disagreement and neutrality. Statements such as feeling flattered if approached romantically by a member of the same sex (mean = 2.61), feeling comfortable if approached by a member of the same sex (mean = 2.43), being attractive to the members of the same sex ($W=2.81$), and feeling comfortable being attracted to a member of the same sex (mean = 2.54) all received lower mean scores, indicating disagreement or neutrality towards these scenarios. These responses suggest varying levels of discomfort or uncertainty regarding same-sex attraction or advances, potentially reflecting societal norms or personal beliefs around sexuality. This is in line with the results of the study of Competente (2021), who highlighted persistent challenges regarding acceptance of homosexuality among teachers. However, it can be noted that majority of the respondents are heterosexual individuals, specifically females, which could explain the results. Nebot-Garcia et al. (2022) suggests the possibility that traditional norms restrict behavioral expression of sexuality among these individuals. Silva (2019) concluded that this situation suggests that straight identification is due partly to embeddedness in straight culture and enjoyment of straight privilege and cannot be considered homophobia.

The overall mean score of 3.38 indicates a neutral stance towards homosexuality among the respondents. This suggests a mixed pattern of attitudes, with some aspects of acceptance and comfort alongside areas of hesitation or disagreement.

Table 3. Respondents' Negative Attitudes Toward Homosexuality

Negative Attitudes	Weighted Mean (N=89)	SD	Description
1. A spouse/partner attracted to any member of their sex make me feel uncomfortable.	3.48	1.13	Agree
2. If a member of sex makes an advance attempt towards me, I would feel offended and angry.	3.04	.96	Neutral
3. I would feel uncomfortable if I learn that my boss is homosexual.	2.01	.78	Disagree
4. I would feel uncomfortable if I learn that my neighbor is a homosexual.	1.87	.73	Disagree
5. I would feel uncomfortable if I learn that my son's/daughter's teacher is a homosexual.	1.94	.76	Disagree
6. I would be upset if I learn that my brother or sister is homosexual.	2.09	1.02	Disagree
7. I would feel that I have failed as a parent if I learn that my child is a homosexual.	2.12	1.02	Disagree
8. I would feel disappointed if I learn that my child is homosexual	2.18	1.13	Disagree
9. I would feel nervous being in a group of homosexuals.	2.02	.94	Disagree
10. It would disturb me to find out that my doctor is homosexual.	1.85	.78	Disagree
Overall	2.27	.93	Disagree

Legend: WM= Weighted Mean, 4.21-5.00 = Strongly Agree, 3.41-4.20 = Agree, 2.61-3.40 = Neutral, 1.81-2.60 = Disagree, 1.00-1.80 = Strongly Disagree

Table 3 presents the predominant attitudes of the respondents when prompted negative statements from the survey.

The statement of feeling uncomfortable with a spouse or partner attracted to any member of their sex (mean = 3.48) received agreement from respondents. This response suggests a level of discomfort or unease with the idea of homosexuality within close familial relationships. Competente (2021) discussed that acceptability of homosexuality is a difficulty when it collides with the teachings of religion and what is perceived as a social norm for genders.

In connection, they stood neutral to feeling offended or angry when a member of their sex approach them in a romantic or sexual manner ($M=3.04$). This neutral response indicates that teachers did not exhibit strong emotions of offense or anger towards the prospect of a same-gender romantic or sexual advance. It suggests a lack of strong inclination towards either accepting or rejecting such advances, reflecting a stance of indecision.

Conversely, respondents expressed disagreement with statements indicating discomfort or negative feelings towards homosexuals in other social contexts. For instance, respondents disagreed with feeling uncomfortable if their boss (mean = 2.01), neighbor (mean =

1.87), child's teacher (mean = 1.94), or even their child's doctor ($W=1.85$) is homosexual. The respondents also expressed their disagreement in a statement that they get nervous being a group of homosexuals ($W=2.02$). This suggests a rejection of prejudice or discrimination based on sexual orientation in professional and neighborhood settings. Studies that considered samples of US teachers found that teachers with sexual minority inclination have more favorable feelings toward bisexual and homosexual individuals (Foy & Hodge, 2016; Stucky et al., 2020) and family members (Foy & Hodge, 2016).

Furthermore, respondents disagreed with statements suggesting negative emotions towards homosexuality within family dynamics. These included feeling that they have failed as a parent if their child is homosexual (mean = 2.12) and feeling disappointed upon learning about their child's homosexuality (mean = 2.18). These responses indicate a rejection of societal pressures or expectations that equate homosexuality with failure or disappointment in parenting. Also, they disagreed with the statements indicating that they would be upset to learn that their siblings are homosexuals ($W=2.09$). This finding may imply that teachers exhibit a level of acceptance or tolerance towards homosexuality within their own families. This is similar to the study of McNeil, Ellis, and Eccles (2017) observing varied attitudes among pre-service teachers toward LGBT individuals. According to Mayock, Bryan, and Carr (2018) found that Irish secondary school teachers hold a spectrum of attitudes toward LGBT students, ranging from positive support to a lack of awareness.

The overall mean score of 2.27 indicates a general disagreement with negative attitudes towards homosexuality among the respondents. This suggests a prevailing sentiment of tolerance and acceptance towards LGBTQ+ individuals within the surveyed population. D'urso and Symonds (2021) underscored the importance of studying teachers' attitudes and perceptions (Gururaj et al., 2023) toward homosexuality in elucidating their capacity for implementing truly inclusive pedagogy.

Table 4. Analysis Of Variance for Respondents' Attitudes Toward Homosexuality When Grouped According to Age

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Positive Attitude towards homosexuality	Between Groups	.755	5	.151	.998	.424
	Within Groups	12.564	83	.151		
	Total	13.319	88			
Negative Attitude towards homosexuality	Between Groups	3.288	5	.658	1.673	.150
	Within Groups	32.622	83	.393		
	Total	35.910	88			

*differences between group means statistically significant at p -value < 0.05

Table 4 presents an analysis of variance between age and attitudes towards homosexuality, focusing on both positive and negative attitudes. The data revealed that for positive attitudes towards homosexuality, there was no statistically significant difference found among different age groups ($F = 0.998$, $p = 0.424$). Similarly, for negative attitudes towards homosexuality, no statistically significant difference was observed based on age ($F = 1.673$, $p = 0.150$). These results suggest that age may not be a significant factor in predicting attitudes towards homosexuality in the studied population. This contrasts with the results of several studies. In terms of age, Baiocco et al. (2020), Grigoropoulos (2022), Hall & Rodgers (2019) and Page (2017) found out that younger teachers tend to have lower levels of sexual prejudice and feel more comfortable dealing with homosexuals than older teachers of higher seniority. Cailing (2024) also states that for both males and females, the greater the age, the more positive attitudes toward homosexuality.

People of different ages in the group tend to have similar attitudes toward homosexuality. In simpler terms, whether a teacher is young or old doesn't seem to affect how they feel about homosexuality. This finding could indicate that factors other than age, like cultural background or personal beliefs, might play a bigger role in shaping attitudes toward homosexuality in the given population. A study conducted among male teachers in State Universities and Colleges (SUCs) in Iloilo, Philippines, found that age was not a significant predictor of their attitudes towards homosexuality. The study revealed that male teachers' knowledge about homosexuality varied based on marital status and religion, but not significantly by age, educational attainment, place of residence, family environment, or peer influence (Dizon, 2015). It is essential to recognize that attitudes are multifaceted and influenced by various factors beyond age.

Table 5. Analysis Of Variance for Respondents' Attitudes Toward Homosexuality When Grouped According to Sexual Orientation

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Positive Attitude towards homosexuality	Between Groups	2.480	2	1.240	9.837	.000*
	Within Groups	10.839	86	.126		
	Total	13.319	88			
Negative Attitude towards homosexuality	Between Groups	3.704	2	1.852	4.945	.009*
	Within Groups	32.206	86	.374		
	Total	35.910	88			

*differences between group means statistically significant at p -value < 0.05

Table 5 presents the analysis of variance (ANOVA) between the respondents' sexual orientation and their attitudes towards homosexuality, examining both positive and negative attitudes. For positive attitudes towards homosexuality, a significant difference was found among different sexual orientations ($F = 9.837$, $p = 0.001$). Similarly, for negative attitudes, a significant difference was observed ($F = 4.945$, $p = 0.009$). These results show that attitudes toward homosexuality are diverse and influenced by sexual orientation. They indicate that people's views on homosexuality vary among different sexual orientation groups.

This finding is supported by the study of Reyes et al. (2019) about Religiosity, Gender Role Beliefs, and Attitudes Toward Lesbians and Gays in the Philippines that not only age as the factor but also about the existence of religiosity, gender role beliefs, and attitudes toward lesbians and gay men showed a significant relationship. Another study supporting the significant relationship of sexual orientation as a factor stating that sex appeared to be more influential factor causing significant differences between male and female in terms of sexual orientation with male's inclination toward masculinity and female's inclination toward femininity (Badjanova, et al., 2017). Foy and Hodge (2016) and Stucky et al. (2020) found that heterosexual teachers exhibited higher levels of prejudice compared to homosexual teachers. Similarly, Cailing (2024) determined that males generally give more negative attitudes toward lesbians and gays compared to females. However, these findings contradict previous studies such as those by Grigoropoulos (2022), Hall & Rodgers (2019), and Stucky et al. (2020), which reported no significant gender differences in attitudes.

Table 6. Post Hoc Test for Respondents' Attitudes Toward Homosexuality When Grouped According to Sexual Orientation

<i>Dependent Variable</i>	<i>(I) Sexual Orientation</i>	<i>(J) Sexual Orientation</i>	<i>Mean Difference (I-J)</i>	<i>Std. Error</i>	<i>Sig.</i>
Positive Attitude towards homosexuality	hetero male	hetero female	-.18816	.09382	.117
		homosexual(LGBTQIA+)	-.46839*	.10715	.000
	hetero female	hetero male	.18816	.09382	.117
		homosexual(LGBTQIA+)	-.28023*	.09100	.008
Negative Attitude towards homosexuality	Homosexual (LGBTQIA+)	hetero male	.46839*	.10715	.000
		hetero female	.28023*	.09100	.008
	hetero male	hetero female	.37778	.16173	.056
		homosexual(LGBTQIA+)	.56957*	.18470	.008
	hetero female	hetero male	-.37778	.16173	.056
		homosexual(LGBTQIA+)	.19179	.15686	.443
	Homosexual (LGBTQIA+)	hetero male	-.56957*	.18470	.008
		hetero female	-.19179	.15686	.443

*differences between group means statistically significant at $p\text{-value} < 0.05$

Tukey Honestly Significant Difference (HSD) post hoc tests were conducted to further examine pairwise differences in attitudes towards homosexuality across different sexual identities, focusing on both positive and negative attitudes.

Table 6 presents the data indicating significant differences in positive attitudes towards homosexuality among heterosexual males compared to heterosexual females ($p = 0.008$) and individuals identifying as homosexual (LGBTQIA+) ($p = 0.001$). Herek and McLemore (2013) contend that heterosexual men frequently demonstrate sexual prejudice as a means of reaffirming their own masculinity and denouncing men who diverge from conventional gender norms. Expanding on this theoretical perspective, Gegenfurtner (2021) posits a comparable pattern within the teaching profession, indicating that females and individuals identifying as homosexual, who might experience less pressure to adhere strictly to traditional gender roles, often hold more favorable attitudes toward homosexuality.

For negative attitudes towards homosexuality, the data revealed that heterosexual males demonstrated significantly lower negative attitudes compared to individuals identifying as homosexual (LGBTQIA+) ($p = 0.008$). These results suggest that individuals identifying as homosexual (LGBTQIA+) generally exhibit more positive attitudes towards homosexuality compared to heterosexual individuals. Additionally, heterosexual males tend to have more positive attitudes than heterosexual females, although this difference is not statistically significant for negative attitudes.

Supporting these results, a study by Bettinsoli, Suppes, and Napier (2015) conducted across 23 countries found that negative attitudes towards gay men and lesbian women were associated with the perception that they violate traditional gender norms. However, cultural contexts played a significant role, with variations observed in countries like China, India, and South Korea. This underscores the impact of cultural norms on attitudes towards homosexuality and the complexity of gender norms in shaping these attitudes. As notable exceptions, Heras-Sevilla and Ortega-Sánchez (2020) reported that Spanish male pre-service teachers had more negative attitudes toward homosexuality than female teachers; and Klocke et al. (2019) found that German female in-service teachers intervened more frequently against homophobia than male in-service teachers.

Furthermore, research by Lee and Mutz (2018) in the U.S. identified several factors contributing to increased support for same-sex marriage, including increased interpersonal contact with LGBTQ+ individuals, declining religiosity, and higher levels of education. These findings emphasize the role of social interactions and education in influencing attitudes towards homosexuality, supporting the notion that exposure to diverse perspectives can foster more positive attitudes.

Additionally, studies focusing on Southeast Asia (Anand, 2016) have highlighted various factors associated with homonegative attitudes, including gender, age, education, religion, and intergroup contact. Women generally tend to have less homonegative attitudes than men, indicating the importance of understanding regional variations in attitudes for promoting inclusivity.

These findings underscore the multifaceted nature of attitudes towards homosexuality, shaped by factors such as gender norms, cultural

contexts, social interactions, and education. Recognizing these nuances can inform targeted interventions aimed at reducing prejudice and promoting acceptance within diverse communities.

Table 7. Analysis Of Variance for Respondents' Attitudes Toward Homosexuality When Grouped According to Religion

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Positive Attitude towards homosexuality	Between Groups	.118	2	.059	.384	.682
	Within Groups	13.201	86	.154		
	Total	13.319	88			
Negative Attitude towards homosexuality	Between Groups	1.036	2	.518	1.277	.284
	Within Groups	34.874	86	.406		
	Total	35.910	88			

*differences between group means statistically significant at p -value < 0.05

Table 7 presents an analysis of variance (ANOVA) between the respondents' religion and their attitudes towards homosexuality, focusing on both positive and negative attitudes. For positive attitudes towards homosexuality, no significant differences were found among different religious groups ($F = 0.384$, $p = 0.682$). Similarly, for negative attitudes towards homosexuality, no significant differences were observed based on religion ($F = 1.277$, $p = 0.284$). These results suggest that religion may not play a significant role in predicting attitudes towards homosexuality in the studied population.

Supporting this finding, the study on Indian engineering students examined various factors influencing attitudes towards homosexuality, including religiosity. Interestingly, religiosity was not found to be a significant predictor of attitudes towards homosexuality among the participants. Instead, factors such as friends' acceptability of homosexuality, just-world belief, and exposure to LGBTQ celebrities were significant predictors (Tasnim, 2021).

Similarly, the study on the effect of religiosity on attitudes towards homosexuality found that while there was a relationship between religiosity and attitudes, it was not statistically significant (Smith et al., 2008). Participants exhibited significant changes in attitudes based on the type of image they were exposed to, indicating that other factors may influence attitudes towards homosexuality more strongly than religiosity alone.

However, it can be noted from the data that the respondents are divided unevenly in terms of their religion. Only 3 (3.4%) out of 89 respondents were Islam while the majority is Roman Catholic (75.3%) and Born-Again Christian (21.3%). This might have affected the results because if the respondents from a particular religion are overrepresented or underrepresented in the sample, it can introduce bias into the study.

These findings challenge the notion that religion, particularly those with conservative theology, is a strong predictor of negative attitudes towards homosexuality. While previous research has suggested this relationship, the studies discussed here did not find strong evidence to support it. Instead, they highlight the complexity of factors influencing attitudes towards homosexuality and suggest that personal beliefs, social influences, and exposure to diverse perspectives may play significant roles in shaping attitudes.

Table 8. Analysis Of Variance for Respondents' Attitudes Toward Homosexuality When Grouped According to Educational Attainment

		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Positive Attitude towards homosexuality	Between Groups	.121	2	.061	.395	.675
	Within Groups	13.198	86	.153		
	Total	13.319	88			
Negative Attitude towards homosexuality	Between Groups	.454	2	.227	.551	.579
	Within Groups	35.456	86	.412		
	Total	35.910	88			

*differences between group means statistically significant at p -value < 0.05

Table 8 presents an analysis of variance (ANOVA) which revealed no significant differences in attitudes towards homosexuality based on educational attainment. For positive attitudes, $F(2, 86) = 0.395$, $p = 0.675$, and for negative attitudes, $F(2, 86) = 0.551$, $p = 0.579$. These findings suggest that educational attainment may not play a significant role in shaping attitudes towards homosexuality in the studied population.

A study by Competente (2021) in Naga City, Philippines on attitudes towards homosexuality among teachers and administrators in public schools, found that both groups held moderate positive attitudes and high negative attitudes toward homosexuality. However, no significant differences were observed between teachers and administrators, indicating that educational attainment did not influence attitudes toward homosexuality in this context.

Similarly, Chen et al. (n.d.) investigated attitudes toward homosexuality among Chinese high school and college students. Despite utilizing the Chinese adaptation of Herek's Attitudes Toward Lesbians and Gay Men scale (ATLG), the study found no significant differences in attitudes between high school and college students. However, gender differences significantly influenced student sentiments toward the homosexual population, suggesting that other factors beyond educational attainment play a more prominent role in shaping attitudes. However, these contrast to the result of Takács & Szalma (2011) stating that a higher educational level is related

to greater tolerance toward homosexuality.

These findings collectively suggest that while educational attainment alone may not significantly impact attitudes toward homosexuality, other factors such as cultural norms, personal beliefs, and exposure to diverse perspectives likely contribute to individuals' attitudes. Therefore, educators and policymakers should focus on creating inclusive environments that foster understanding and acceptance of sexual diversity, regardless of individuals' educational levels.

Furthermore, future research could explore additional variables such as religious beliefs and exposure to LGBTQ+ content to better understand the complex interplay between education and attitudes toward homosexuality. By examining these factors comprehensively, a more nuanced understanding of the determinants of attitudes toward homosexuality can be achieved, leading to more effective interventions and policies aimed at promoting inclusivity and acceptance.

Table 9. Correlation Analysis of Respondents' Attitudes Toward Homosexuality in Terms of Age, Sexual Orientation, Religion, And Educational Attainment

Profile	r-value	Relationship strength	p-value	remarks
<i>Positive Attitudes</i>				
age	-.027	Weak	.798	not significant
sexual orientation	.427	Moderate	.000	significant
religion	-.086	Very Weak	.421	not significant
educational attainment	-.048	Very Weak	.658	not significant
<i>Negative Attitudes</i>				
age	.181	Very Weak	.089	not significant
sexual orientation	-.313	Weak	.003	significant
religion	.167	Very Weak	.117	not significant
educational attainment	.039	Very Weak	.719	not significant

**Correlation is significant at 0.05 significance level; Relationship Strength Scale: 1 (Perfect), ± 0.80 to ± 0.99 (Very Strong), ± 0.61 to ± 0.79 (Strong), ± 0.41 to ± 0.61 (Moderate), ± 0.21 to ± 0.40 (Weak), ± 0.01 to ± 0.20 (Very Weak)*

Table 9 presents the correlation analysis between respondents' attitudes toward homosexuality and various demographic variables including age, sexual orientation, religion, and educational attainment.

For positive attitudes toward homosexuality, sexual orientation showed a statistically significant moderate positive correlation ($r = 0.427$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that individuals who identify with a particular sexual orientation tend to exhibit more positive attitudes toward homosexuality. Age, religion, and educational attainment did not show statistically significant correlations with positive attitudes toward homosexuality (all p -values > 0.05).

For negative attitudes toward homosexuality, sexual orientation also exhibited a statistically significant weak negative correlation ($r = -0.313$, $p = 0.003$), suggesting that individuals who identify with a particular sexual orientation tend to hold fewer negative attitudes toward homosexuality. Age, religion, and educational attainment did not show statistically significant correlations with negative attitudes toward homosexuality (all p -values > 0.05).

These findings suggest that sexual orientation is a significant factor of both positive and negative attitudes toward homosexuality, with individuals who identify with a particular sexual orientation expressing more positive attitudes and fewer negative attitudes. However, age, religion, and educational attainment did not significantly relate to attitudes toward homosexuality in this study.

Heras-Sevilla and Ortega-Sánchez (2020) found that male pre-service teachers in Spain tended to show more negative attitudes toward homosexuality compared to their female counterparts. Similarly, Klocke et al. (2019) observed differences in attitudes between male and female in-service teachers in Germany, with females being more proactive against homophobia. These findings align with broader research indicating higher levels of sexual prejudice among cisgender heterosexual men compared to women, particularly directed toward gay men (Herek, 2002; Petersen & Hyde, 2010).

Furthermore, studies by Foy and Hodge (2016) and Stucky et al. (2020) highlight the prevalence of prejudice among heterosexual teachers compared to their homosexual counterparts. This underscores the importance of considering the perspectives and experiences of LGBTQIA+ individuals within educational contexts. Additionally, Gegenfurtner et al. (2023) propose that non-heteronormative teachers may hold more positive views toward students with similar orientations, suggesting the potential impact of teacher diversity on attitudes toward sexual and gender diversity.

These findings contribute to the understanding of the complex interplay between sexual orientation, attitudes toward homosexuality, and the broader social and cultural context within educational settings. They emphasize the need for inclusive practices and support systems to create environments where all individuals, regardless of sexual orientation or gender identity, feel respected and valued (Herek & McLemore, 2013; Casey et al., 2019; Gegenfurtner & Gebhardt, 2017).

Conclusion

This study concludes that high school teachers generally hold positive attitudes toward homosexuality, as evidenced by their ease and

acceptance of interacting with homosexuals in social and professional settings. However, there are also instances of disagreement or neutrality, especially concerning scenarios involving same-sex attraction, indicating varying levels of discomfort or uncertainty. Overall, the findings present a mixed pattern of attitudes, encompassing both acceptance and hesitation towards homosexuality.

Similarly, the data suggests predominantly fewer negative attitudes towards homosexuality, with respondents largely rejecting statements indicating discomfort or negative feelings in various social and familial contexts. This rejection of prejudice aligns with broader trends indicating increased acceptance and tolerance towards LGBTQ+ individuals among teachers. While some neutrality was noted regarding same-gender romantic or sexual advances, the overall sentiment expressed by respondents tends towards tolerance and acceptance.

Moreover, it is concluded that age, religion, and educational attainment of teachers do not appear to be significant predictors of attitudes toward homosexuality among them, as no statistically significant differences were observed in either positive or negative attitudes. However, the data highlights significant differences found in both positive and negative attitudes based on the respondents' sexual orientation. Specifically, significant differences in positive attitudes towards homosexuality among heterosexual males compared to both heterosexual females and individuals identifying as homosexual (LGBTQIA+). Additionally, heterosexual males exhibit significantly negative attitudes towards homosexuality compared to individuals identifying as homosexual (LGBTQIA+), suggesting a trend of more positive attitudes among the latter group.

In terms of correlates, the analysis revealed that sexual orientation is a significant predictor of both positive and negative attitudes toward homosexuality. Specifically, individuals who identify with a particular sexual orientation tend to exhibit more positive attitudes and fewer negative attitudes towards homosexuality. This underscores the importance of considering sexual orientation in understanding and addressing attitudes towards LGBTQ+ individuals within educational settings. However, age, religion, and educational attainment did not show statistically significant correlations with attitudes toward homosexuality in this study.

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